

Generic Polynomial Inflationary Potentials and Cosmological Perturbations

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By

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Abstract

We study the hybrid model of inflation for chaotic polynomial like potentials, $V(\phi) = V_0 + \lambda_p \phi^p$, for different values of p . Inflationary dynamics of the hybrid inflation are analyzed under slow-roll approximation such that the potential energy of the inflaton field dominates over its kinetic energy during inflation. Inflation predicts the scalar and tensor perturbations in the early universe. The scalar and tensor mode of primordial perturbations set the initial conditions for the large-scale structure formation of universe. Spectrum of scalar perturbations in terms of scalar spectral index, n_s is evaluated. The tensor perturbations contribute to another observable parameter, tensor to scalar ratio r , that predicts the existence of primordial gravitational waves in the early universe. We analyzed the parametric space provided by the inflationary potentials and compared our results with the recent Planck's data. The predictions of observational parameters are found to be outside of the Planck's bounds. To probe the empirical data, fermionic radiative correction is added to the hybrid potential which reduces the tensor to scalar ratio, r , and predicts red-tilted scalar spectral index, n_s . Fermionic radiative correction can couple with the inflaton field and provides the mechanism for re-heating of the universe after inflation ends.

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Introduction

Observation of the universe remained part time joy and fear of humanity since antiquity. The struggle of consideration that there exists an external world which is enormous in its size enforced humans to ponder over its reality and deconstruct it into parts. Structure of the universe and its beginning remained subjects of interests for philosophers and scientists for centuries. But the most precise mathematical description, we found till today, known as General Theory of Relativity (GR), formulated by Albert Einstein in 1916. The discovery of GR led to birth of modern cosmology. The notion of analyzing the universe under equations of GR made different discoveries possible. This led to developments of simpler dynamical models of the universe by Lemaitre and Friedmann on the following hypotheses.

1. The universe is considered to be homogeneous and isotropic at large scales.
2. The geometry and gravitational properties are described by the General Theory of Relativity.

Another major discovery was expansion of the universe realized by Hubble during his examination of velocities of different stellar objects in the cosmos. He found that objects which were far from our galaxy happened to be going farther with greater velocities than the objects which were closer to us [1]. The expansion of universe was pointing towards the hypothesis that universe started out in hot dense state, expanded, and then cooled down. The notion later on called as the Big Bang Model. The most concrete evidence of Big Bang Model came through accidental discovery of Cosmic Microwave Background Radiation (CMBR) by Penzias and Wilson in 1965 [2]. The CMBR appeared to be one of the greatest discovery of previous century

because it enable us to examine the history of the observable universe through analysis of this radiation. CMBR raises different questions on the classical description of the universe making problems for the Big Bang Model such as horizon, flatness, and magnetic monopoles conundrums. Different paradigms are established to resolve these fine-tuning issues of Big Bang Model and predict the initial conditions. Inflation is one such paradigm to resolve cosmological problems based on the dynamics of scalar fields.

In order to understand the implications of the inflation, we will discuss the fundamental dynamics of the universe governed by Friedmann Equations in the chapter 1. Chapter 2 frames the problem of Big Bang Cosmology in rigorous way by defining the features of Hubble radius and causality. Inflation, as solution of Big Bang Problems, is characterized by accelerated expansion for a finite amount of time. Development of inflationary scenario, slow-roll approximation, and role of field theory is considered under chapter 3. There are different models of inflation each with its own predictive power. Hybrid Inflation is one such model where inflation is characterized by two kinds of scalar fields. In chapter 4, hybrid inflationary scenario is defined in the realm of chaotic inflation, different slow-roll parameters are calculated. Furthermore, numerical results are produced by doing numerical calculations for predictions of different observables which are studied in light of Planck's recent data. Chapter 6 is based on introducing the radiative corrections in hybrid inflationary potential. For predictive analysis, slow-roll parameters are considered and calculated. Similarly, numerical results of radiatively corrected hybrid inflation are examined.

Chapter 1

Standard Big Bang Cosmology

1.1 Cosmological Principle

Cosmological Principle (CP) has its roots in the Copernican idea of no privilege to any observer in the universe. It defines the rudimentary background for developing almost all of the cosmological models. CP in its basic assumptions can be stated as two invariances [3]:

1. Homogeneity: The universe is invariant under translational transformation.
2. Isotropy: The universe is invariant under rotational transformation.

1.1.1 Homogeneity

Homogeneity can be understood by considering a uniform fluid in which observer can be situated at any place but it looks the same everywhere. It means, in simpler terms, that any translation of galactic objects leaves the galactic distribution invariant. There is no preferred location for observations.

1.1.2 Isotropy

Isotropy confines the idea that there is no preferred direction in the universe. There is no way demarcate the north from the south or vice versa. The direction can

be distinguished for someone living on the sphere until some matter or objects introduced in it. The CMBR is the major experimental proof of the universe being homogeneous and isotropic.

1.2 Friedmann-Robertson-Walker (FRW) Universe

Assuming the conditions of isotropy and homogeneity for the universe at large scales, in spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) , one can write FRW [4, 5, 6] metric for such universe.

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + a^2(t) \left(\frac{dr^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2) \right), \quad (1.1)$$

The $a(t)$ is called as the scale factor of the universe, the expansion of universe is proportional to the scale factor $a(t)$. The parameter k represents the geometry or shape of the universe [7]. There are three possible configurations for the parameter k ; closed universe, open universe, flat universe.

1.2.1 Geometry of the Universe

Closed Universe ($k = +1$)

For a universe with positive k value, the shape will be spherical or positively curved. Such universe is called as closed universe.

Open Universe ($k = -1$)

The universe with negative value of k will follow hyperbolic geometry and known as open universe.

Flat Universe ($k = 0$)

$k = 0$ depicts the universe with zero curvature or classical Euclidean space in which all laws of Euclidean geometry are valid [8]. Our universe is considered to follow flat geometry.

1.2.2 Einstein's Field Equations in FRW Cosmology

The Einstein's field equations which dictate the structure of space-time and dynamics of the universe [9] are given as

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R = 8\pi GT_{\mu\nu}, \quad (1.2)$$

where $G_{\mu\nu} = 8\pi GT_{\mu\nu}$ is known as Einstein tensor, $R_{\mu\nu}$ is Ricci tensor, R is Ricci scalar, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is metric tensor, G is gravitational constant, and $T_{\mu\nu}$ is energy-momentum tensor. Considering the condition of perfect fluid and writing down the energy-momentum tensor which can be represented with following equation.

$$T^{\mu\nu} = (P + \rho)u^\mu u^\nu - g^{\mu\nu}P, \quad (1.3)$$

where P is the pressure, ρ is the energy density, $u^\mu = (1, 0, 0, 0)$ is the four velocity in co-moving coordinates then $T^{\mu\nu}$ and $g_{\mu\nu}$ respectively,

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & P & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & P & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & P \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1.4)$$

$$g^{\mu\nu} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -a^2(t)(1 - kr^2)^{-1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -a^2(t)r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -a^2(t)r^2 \sin^2\theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.5)$$

The Einstein's field eq. (1.2) using eqs. (1.5) and (1.6) yields the famous Friedmann Equations when $c = 1$.

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho - \frac{k}{a^2} + \frac{\Lambda}{3}, \quad (1.6)$$

$$\left(\frac{\ddot{a}}{a}\right) = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\rho + 3p) + \frac{\Lambda}{3}, \quad (1.7)$$

where $H = \frac{\dot{a}}{a}$ known as Hubble's parameter having unit of inverse time which defines the expansion rate of the universe. If H is positive, universe is expanding and if negative then universe is contracting. The Hubble parameter sets the constraints on the age and size of observable universe.

1.2.3 Fluid Equation and Energy Content of the Universe

The Friedmann equations determine the basic physics behind evolution of the universe but there is another equation that is derivable from eqs. (1.6) and (1.7) or by imposing the conservation law on stress-energy tensor.

$$\nabla_{\mu} T^{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (1.8)$$

This leads to the continuity equation.

$$\dot{\rho} + 3 \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right) (\rho + p) = 0, \quad (1.9)$$

which specifies energy content of the universe in different epochs. The equation of state can be utilized to re-frame the eq. (1.9).

$$\omega = p/\rho. \quad (1.10)$$

We use equation of state, eq. (1.10), in eq. (1.9) to eliminate p and obtain

$$\frac{\dot{\rho}}{\rho} + 3 \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right) (1 + \omega) = 0, \quad (1.11)$$

$$\frac{\dot{\rho}}{\rho} = - \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right) 3(1 + \omega), \quad (1.12)$$

Solving the eq. (1.12), we can infer the scale factor with respect to the energy density as

$$\rho \propto a^{-3(1+\omega)}, \quad (1.13)$$

Combining eq. (1.13) with eq. (1.6) , we can evaluate the growth of scale factor with respect to time as

$$a \propto t^{\frac{2}{3(1+\omega)}} \quad (1.14)$$

Therefore, the evolution of energy density in the universe relative to different epochs can be summarized in the following manner.

- **Matter dominated universe:** $\omega = 0$, the energy density varies as $\rho \propto a^{-3}$ whereas variation of scale factor increases $a \propto t^{\frac{2}{3}}$.
- **Radiation dominated universe:** The value of $\omega = \frac{1}{3}$, the energy density decreases with a^{-4} [?], the extra contribution is coming from the decrement in photon's energy due to expansion of the universe. Scale factor increases in form of $a \propto t^{\frac{2}{3}}$.
- **Vacuum dominated universe:** $\omega = -1$ with constant energy density. The scale factor, in this case, grows with exponential expansion $a \propto e^{Ht}$.

1.3 Causality and Space-Time

Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity (SR) defines the causal features of the universe. Light has the ultimate element of defining the causality because it's speed is universally constant. Therefore, in FRW cosmology, light determines the causal elements. The path followed by the light is known as null geodesic $ds^2 = 0$. In order to comprehend this, it's appropriate to define convenient quantity known as conformal time.

$$\tau = \int \frac{dt}{a(t)}. \quad (1.15)$$

This can be utilized to write the Minkowski metric from the FRW metric with involvement of conformal factor $a(\tau)$ for flat universe $k = 0$,

$$ds^2 = a(\tau)^2 (-d\tau^2 + dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2)) \equiv a(\tau^2)\eta_{\mu\nu}dx^\mu dx^\nu. \quad (1.16)$$

However, the path of light can be written with the help of following metric,

$$ds^2 = a(\tau)^2 (-d\tau^2 + dr^2) . \quad (1.17)$$

The path followed by the light can define the particle horizon or the maximal distance that light can achieve from some initial time t_i to final time t_f .

$$\Delta r = \int_{t_i}^{t_f} \frac{dt}{a(t)} . \quad (1.18)$$

The eq. (1.18) defines the comoving particle horizon. It is the farthest distance that light can travel since the beginning of the universe if we consider the initial time t_i to be the time of singularity. The particle horizon explains the distance to which light could travel in the finite time as universe had a beginning as proposed by the Big Bang Model and made causal connections [11]. Understanding the causality is basic ingredient for comprehending the need of inflationary scenario and why there are certain problems with the Big Bang Cosmology.

Chapter 2

Problems of Big Bang Cosmology

2.1 Shortcomings of Big Bang Model

Due to successes of CMBR and idea of Hubble's expansion of the universe along with nucleosynthesis made the Big Bang Model as the most successful and viable description of the universe both theoretically and experimentally [12]. Despite the triumph of Big Bang Model, there are still certain shortcomings which restricts the predictions of Big Bang Cosmology in certain aspects. CMBR agrees with the Cosmological Principle defining the homogeneity of the universe. For universe to be homogeneous, all of its regions must be causally connected. The universe must be capable of developing thermal equilibrium everywhere. This is known as Horizon Problem. Horizon problem characterizes that CMBR which we observe today is emitted out of the regions which were not in any causal contact before [13]. Although, the experiments such as Cosmic Background Explorer (COBE) shows that CMBR is highly homogeneous in all directions with minimum anomalies or anisotropies. Similarly, universe appears to be extraordinarily flat which requires explanation because little distortions due to energy density in the early universe would enforce the universe to move away from flatness. This apparent flatness, which we observe today, can only happen due to remarkable fine tuning of the universe in its early stages. Big Bang Model does not give any answer to this question. There is also existence of thermal fluctuations, anisotropies in the CMBR, and magnetic

monopoles which is unexplained in the Big Bang Model of Cosmology. Ultimately, density perturbations reason for the large scale structure formation of the universe is not implied in the Big Bang Model. We will describe the horizon flatness, and magnetic monopoles problems in theoretical terms to emphasize on their existence and search for solution.

2.2 Horizon Problem

We have already defined the particle horizon τ in the previous section which explains the causal relationship of the universe or the maximal distance light can travel since the beginning of the universe. Rewriting the equations for time light takes from 0 to time t .

$$\tau \equiv \int_0^t \frac{dt}{a(t)},$$

We rewrite the above expression in H by using its relation $H = \frac{\dot{a}}{a} = \frac{da}{a dt}$.

$$\tau \equiv \int_0^a \frac{da}{Ha^2} = \int_0^a d \ln a \left(\frac{1}{aH} \right), \quad (2.1)$$

The expression for the particle horizon has been factored in the form of more special and useful quantity known as comoving Hubble radius $\left(\frac{1}{aH} \right)$. The technical calculations of the particle horizon shows that only 1° angle in the sky was inside the casual connection after the era of decoupling which happened 380,000 years later after the event of Big Bang. The evolution of a universe comprising of fluid with state equation $\omega \equiv p/\rho$ is given as:

$$\left(\frac{1}{aH} \right) \propto a^{\frac{1}{2}(1+3\omega)}, \quad (2.2)$$

It was usual to assume that comoving Hubble radius increases with evolution of universe. And singularity occurs at the instant of conformal time $\tau = 0$. Everything depends on the sign of the quantity $(1 + 3\omega)$. There is monotonic increase in the

comoving Hubble radius with time which implies that at the time of decoupling the regions were far outside the horizon and causal connections than they are today. Therefore, the relation between matter and radiation dominated epochs with scale factor can be understood by following relation,

$$\tau \propto a(MD). \quad (2.3)$$

$$\tau \propto a^{\frac{1}{2}}(RD). \quad (2.4)$$

Conformal diagrams can also be drawn for eloquent understanding of conventional evolution of the universe and horizon problem under the light of conformal time and horizon scales.

Figure 2.1: Conformal diagram of horizon problem [11].

For instance, in the figure (2.1) we can observe the instant of Big Bang singularity (graphically not actually - hope we could) at conformal time $\tau = 0$ where Einstein's GR fails down, then there is τ_{dec} which shows time at decoupling when CMBR emerged. If we draw past line cones, we see the regions which could be in the causal

contact since the beginning of the universe till time of decoupling or recombination. It is evident that two triangular regions are causally disconnected with each other and there were no reason that these regions could achieve thermal equilibrium. Hence, horizon problem is fundamental issue in the description of Big Bang Model.

2.3 Flatness Problem

Another issue which succumbs to Big Bang Model is the existence of flat universe. Flatness problem lies inside the class of fine-tuning problems. Why universe is extraordinarily fine-tuned to be evolved as flat? Big Bang Model does not provide any answer. Flatness problem can also be defined in the mathematical terms. Recalling the Friedmann equation (1.6) and ignoring the cosmological constant Λ part.

$$H^2 + \frac{k}{a^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{3}\rho,$$

Dividing both side by H^2 ,

$$1 + \frac{k}{H^2 a^2} = \frac{8\pi G}{3H^2}\rho, \quad (2.5)$$

whereas critical density can be defined as $\rho_c = \frac{3H^2}{8\pi G}$.

$$1 + \frac{k}{(aH)^2} = \frac{\rho}{\rho_c}, \quad (2.6)$$

where $\frac{\rho}{\rho_c}$ can be written as Ω ,

$$\frac{k}{(aH)^2} = \Omega - 1. \quad (2.7)$$

In the conventional evolution of the universe, the quantity $|\Omega - 1|$ should deviate from 1 due to increase in the comoving Hubble radius $(aH)^{-1}$ with evolution of the universe [14]. The divergence from $k = 1$ at the Planck's scale is of order:

$$|\Omega_{pl} - 1| \leq \mathcal{O}(10^{-61}). \quad (2.8)$$

The equation (2.8) shows the order of magnitude to which universe was fine tuned for having $k = 1$.

Figure 2.2: Flatness problem: Ω vs t [15]. Evolution of universe needs to be fine-tuned at early stages for keeping k at $k = 0$.

2.4 Magnetic Monopoles Problem

In the early era of universe, the relevant theories are motivated by particle physics. The particle theories are significant for predictions in very early universe ¹. These theories predict existence of topological defects due to phase transitions in the early universe. The topological defects predicted in particle models can be categorized in the following manner. Phase transitions occur due to Spontaneous Symmetry Breaking (SSB) when the universe cools down.

- **Strings**
- **Domain Walls**

¹Also the reason of constructing Quantum Gravity (QG) theories for understanding the phenomena happening in the universe when quantum effects were crucial.

- **Magnetic Monopoles**

Magnetic monopoles are mostly discussed in the particle theory. Existence of magnetic monopoles in the universe is evident by the calculations in Big Bang Model when including the effects of electroweak symmetry breaking [16]. The Big Bang Model predicts that universe would be abundant with magnetic monopoles. However, there is no experimental justification of existence of magnetic monopoles. Therefore, it creates problem for the Big Bang Model.

Chapter 3

An Exposition to Inflationary Paradigm

*“Begin at the beginning,” the King said
gravely, “and go on till you come to the end:
then stop.”*

— Lewis Carroll, Alice in Wonderland

3.1 Introduction to Inflationary Scenario

Big Bang Model, despite its remarkable success, contains different kinds of problems such as horizon, flatness, and magnetic monopoles etc. Physicists were trying to come up models of the universe by which they could rejoice the success of Big Bang Model and simultaneously discover the solutions of problems in Big Bang Model. One of the most popular model proposed which solves these problems is known as Inflation. Inflation solves the Big Bang problems by proposing exponential like expansion in the early universe. Prime inspiration behind exponential expansion could come from the solutions of Einstein’s Field Equations in which universe is filled with cosmological constant ($\omega = -1$). Such de-Sitter model could solve the Big Bang problems but in this case expansion never ends and we find no energy density in the universe (empty universe) which is not the case according to observations. This issue

of de-Sitter model could be corrected by stopping the accelerated expansion of the universe after enough time which is required for solving the Big Bang conundrums. However, physicists took the inspiration from the de-sitter model and the particle physics theories. The first kind of rudimentary inflationary models were proposed by Alexie Starobinsky in 1980 [17] and Alan Guth in 1981 [18]. In 1980's, Guth was examining a class of particle physics theories such as Grand Unified Theories (GUT) and thought if cosmology could be married with GUT in phenomenological style. Different kind of modifications and plethora of models have been suggested since the emergence of inflationary paradigm.

The proposal of rapid expansion solving the Big Bang problems has different consequences. One of the consequence is reduction of comoving Hubble radius for a brief period of time which seemed to be increasing in conventional evolution of the universe. Dynamics of early universe drastically changes if we consider reduction in comoving Hubble radius. It also implies that for inflation to happen, there is need of negative pressures. Although, there must be some physical reason for generating these effects or for driving the inflation. Inspired by particle physics, this is done by proposing a scalar field which evolves according to the inflationary conditions. Field theoretic paradigm operates under different scenarios such as phase transition and slow-rolling of the field. This formalism also provides reasoning behind the production of perturbations which acted as seeds for the large-scale structure formation of the universe. Purpose of inflation is not just to resolve the problems of Big Bang Cosmology but also to create initial conditions for evolution of universe as described by the Big Bang Model. In order to understand inflation as a scenario, we will consider the solutions of Big Bang puzzles in inflation, physics behind it, different inflationary models, certain aspects of field theory, old and new inflation, and dynamics of slow-roll inflation in the next sections.

3.2 Solution of Horizon Problem

Horizon problem was result of constantly increasing comoving Hubble radius¹ during the conventional evolution of universe. It can be solved by proposing elegant notion: reduction of comoving Hubble radius in the early universe for a period of time.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(aH)^{-1} < 0. \quad (3.1)$$

We can analyze this by rewriting the equation for comoving Hubble radius relative to conformal time. Recalling eq. (2.1)

$$\tau \equiv \int_0^a \frac{da}{Ha^2} = \int_0^a d \ln a \left(\frac{1}{aH} \right), \quad (3.2)$$

In the eq. (3.2) τ could be greater than $(aH)^{-1}$ in a way that regions of space which are not in causal contact today but did have communicated in the earlier times. In this way, each region can thermalize and develop causal connections [19]. This could only happen if the scale factor a accelerates so the whole quantity $(aH)^{-1}$ could decrease.

Figure 3.1: Reduction in comoving Hubble radius [7]. Inflation enforces the disconnected regions of space to move into smooth patch.

¹Co-moving Hubble radius has significant role in causality and homogeneity of universe.

The figure (3.1) depicts that comoving hubble radius decreases and gets inside the smooth patch, inflation ends, and then conventional evolution of the universe begins.

3.2.1 Conformal Solution of Horizon Problem

The solution of Horizon problem can also be realized by the conformal diagram.

Figure 3.2: Conformal diagram of solution of horizon problem [11]. Inflation shifts Big Bang singularity backwards in time and comoving Hubble radius moves into the horizon for developing causal connections.

Inflation pushes the conformal time towards the negative infinity. What we thought to be the $\tau = 0$ as the initial singularity was actually the time for the reheating. In this way, the regions which are entering the horizon scales today were actually part in causal contact during inflationary epoch. In this way, homogeneity of CMBR is evident.

3.3 Solution of Flatness Problem

Flatness problem stated that universe is fine-tuned to be flat in the early stages. This could also be considered in terms of increasing comoving Hubble radius. Rewriting the equation for flatness problem. The solution for flatness problem

$$\frac{k}{(aH)^2} = \Omega - 1, \quad (3.3)$$

The reduction in comoving Hubble radius enforces the left side of the equation to be very small. $\frac{d}{dt}(aH)^{-1}$ implies the ratio $\Omega = \frac{\rho}{\rho_c}$ moves towards 1. $\Omega = 1$ is also called as attractor solution. The solution for flatness problem can be interpreted in more physical way as well. For instance, rapid expansion of any curved manifold can flatten the universe as shown in the fig (3.3).

Figure 3.3: Flattening the Curvature [20].

3.4 Summary of Inflationary Conditions

The conditions for inflationary paradigm to function properly are summarized.

- **Reduction in comoving Hubble radius:** All of the other inflationary conditions can be derived by considering the condition of reduction in comoving Hubble radius.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(aH)^{-1} < 0. \quad (3.4)$$

- **Accelerated Expansion:** Accelerated expansion is the crux of inflationary

scenario.

$$\frac{d}{dt}(aH)^{-1} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^{-1} = \frac{d}{dt} \dot{a}^{-1} = -\dot{a}^{-2} \ddot{a} \implies \ddot{a} > 0. \quad (3.5)$$

- **Negative Pressures:** Considering the second Friedmann Equation

$$\left(\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} \right) = -\frac{4\pi G}{3}(\rho + 3p). \quad (3.6)$$

Using $\ddot{a} > 0$ shows that there is need of negative pressures for inflation to happen.

3.5 Old and New Inflation

Inflation is proposed as a field theoretic model. Inflationary solutions such as shrinking of Hubble radius, accelerated expansion, and negative pressures can be conceptualized in terms of evolution of scalar field with particular conditions. In field theory, scalar field depicts spin-0 particles such as Higgs boson. The discovery of fundamental scalar field e.g Higgs field is also one of the motivation of formulation of inflation as field theory. But Higgs field itself is disfavored as consistent formulation of inflationary dynamics. Therefore, another unknown scalar field inflaton was proposed for this purpose. In the early history of inflation, Guth proposed the scalar field as mechanism of mimicking the de-Sitter model for solving the cosmological issues and phase transition for ending the inflation. Scalar field gets trapped in false vacuum state and quantum tunneling occurs to have transition from false vacuum to true vacuum state which rapidly expands as bubbles and ends the inflationary epoch. Right after the ending of inflation, inflaton field decays into other fields or particles (matter and radiation). The process is known as reheating. Reheating is three-step procedure in which inflaton decays into massive bosons whereas fermions are rarely produced, those bosons decay into other particles, and finally the particles produced thermalize with each other [21, 22]. Guth's model had bubble nucleation problems

which is restricted in the occurrence of proper re-heating process. In order to get rid of this issue, Linde [23, 24] and others proposed another model of inflation which is known as New inflation. New inflation was founded on the notion of slow-rolling of inflaton over the potential hill. This model requires second-order phase transition to transit from false vacuum state to true vacuum state but without tunneling mechanism [25]. Linde, later on, proposed another kind of model known as Chaotic Inflation [26] which does not require any kind of phase transition. Different models of inflation like small-field model, large-field model, and hybrid model of inflation [27] have been studied since then [28]. We will discuss the physics of inflation in the next sections.

3.6 Inflation as Field Theoretic Model

Inflation is characterized by scalar field. A scalar field takes unique value at different space-time points. Similarly, the inflaton ϕ , responsible for inflation, also depends on space (x) and time (t). Any dynamical field will have potential $V(\phi)$ and kinetic energy $T(\phi)$ terms. These terms determine the evolution of a scalar field. Our task is to determine under which conditions accelerated expansion can be achieved. Inflation itself does not contain specific form of potential $V(\phi)$, the reason that there are numerous models of inflation exist today. Before going into details of dynamics of inflaton, we would have brief review of field theory.

3.6.1 Field Theory

Field theory is the underlying formalism for comprehending the evolution of scalar fields. Contrary to classical mechanics, where dynamical systems are characterized by Lagrangian, fields are determined by Lagrangian density due to continuous nature of fields. The relation between Lagrangian and Lagrangian density is given by following equation.

$$L = \int \mathcal{L} d^3x. \quad (3.7)$$

As discussed earlier, the scalar field being continuous are determined by space-time $\phi(x, t)$. Considering the potential energy density $V(\phi)$ of the field, Lagrangian density \mathcal{L} becomes this.

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = \frac{1}{2} \partial_\mu \phi \partial^\mu \phi - V(\phi), \quad (3.8)$$

The Euler-Lagrange equations of the relevant Lagrangian density is given by

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \phi} - \frac{d}{dx^\mu} \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_\mu \phi)} \right) = 0, \quad (3.9)$$

whereas stress-energy tensor for the given Lagrangian can be written as

$$T^{\mu\nu} = -\frac{2}{\sqrt{-g}} \frac{\partial (\mathcal{L}_m \sqrt{-g})}{\partial g_{\mu\nu}} = -2 \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}_m}{\partial g_{\mu\nu}} - g^{\mu\nu} \mathcal{L}_m. \quad (3.10)$$

The eq. (3.8) can be considered in the following way for calculating the stress-energy tensor from the eq. (3.10)

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu'\nu'} \partial_{\mu'} \phi \partial_{\nu'} \phi - V(\phi), \quad (3.11)$$

where $g_{\mu\nu} g^{\nu\lambda} = \delta_\mu^\lambda$. Now, taking derivative of $g^{\mu'\nu'}$

$$(\delta g_{\mu\nu}) g^{\nu\lambda} + g_{\mu\nu} \delta g^{\nu\lambda} = 0,$$

$$\delta g^{\mu\nu} = -g^{\nu\nu'} g^{\mu\mu'} \delta g_{\mu'\nu'} \implies \frac{\partial g^{\mu'\nu'}}{\partial g_{\mu\nu}} = -g^{\nu\nu'} g^{\mu\mu'}. \quad (3.12)$$

Hence, stress-energy tensor becomes

$$T^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu \phi \partial^\nu \phi - g^{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{1}{2} \partial_{\nu'} \phi \partial^{\nu'} \phi - V \right). \quad (3.13)$$

In eq. (3.13), the index can be lowered down

$$T_\nu^\mu = g^{\mu\rho} \partial_\rho \phi \partial_\nu \phi - \delta^\mu_\nu \left(\frac{1}{2} \partial_\rho \phi \partial^\rho \phi - V \right), \quad (3.14)$$

In the FRW background, the quantity T_0^0 determines the density ρ while pressure is depicted by $T_j^i = -P\delta_j^i$ quantities. Writing down the Lagrangian density for homogeneous field².

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi). \quad (3.15)$$

By utilizing eq. (3.14), pressure p and energy density ρ can be calculated.

$$p_\phi = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi). \quad (3.16)$$

$$\rho_\phi = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi). \quad (3.17)$$

The equation of state is simply this now,

$$\omega \equiv \frac{p_\phi}{\rho_\phi} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi)}{\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi)}. \quad (3.18)$$

The Friedmann equations and continuity equation can be written again with the help of eq. (3.16) and (3.17) which dictates the evolution of scalar field.

$$H^2 = \left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \left(\frac{1}{2}\dot{\phi}^2 + V(\phi)\right). \quad (3.19)$$

$$\ddot{\phi} + V' + 3H\dot{\phi} = 0. \quad (3.20)$$

The condition for inflation to happen was to attain negative pressure which could be conceptualized by dominating the potential energy term $V(\phi)$ over the kinetic energy $\dot{\phi}$. This approximation $V(\phi) \gg \dot{\phi}$ leads us to Slow-Roll Approximation (SRA).

² $\partial_i\phi = 0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3$

3.6.2 Slow-Roll Approximation

SRA regime is based on ignoring the kinetic energy term in the Friedmann equations.

The Friedmann equations for inflaton field can be stated in the following way,

$$H^2 \approx \frac{8\pi G}{3} V(\phi). \quad (3.21)$$

$$3H\dot{\phi} \approx -V'. \quad (3.22)$$

For SRA validity, there is need not for $\dot{\phi}$ to be negligible but also the $\ddot{\phi}$. This constraint can be implemented by considering the two slow-roll parameters whose smallness is required for inflation to happen naturally [13]. These slow-roll parameters ϵ and η are defined in the following manner.

$$\epsilon \equiv \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{V'(\phi)}{V(\phi)} \right)^2 \ll 1. \quad (3.23)$$

$$\eta \equiv m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{V''(\phi)}{V(\phi)} \right) \ll 1. \quad (3.24)$$

Figure 3.4: Slow-Roll Paradigm

To measure the amount of inflation happened in number of e-foldings, we can

define the following parameter N .

$$N \equiv \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{V(\phi)}{V'(\phi)} \right) d\phi. \quad (3.25)$$

SRA can also be realized in another way known as Hubble Slow-Roll Approximation (HSRA) in which Hubble parameter remains center of attention. HSRA is superior to Potential Slow-Roll Approximation (PSRA) for analytic and geometric explanations [29]. HSRA is studied generically when form of potential is not specified. We will use PSRA in this thesis.

Chapter 4

Proposition of Hybrid Inflation

4.1 Brief Introduction of Hybrid Inflationary Model

There are different kinds of model proposed to solve certain problems which resides in inflationary paradigm such as graceful exit problem, mechanism for ending the inflation, and fine tuning problem [30]. These problems without complications of models remained significant issue in inflationary theory. The ending of inflation can be done through two methodologies; slow-rolling of the field or first-order phase transition. As discussed earlier in the Chapter 3, slow-roll inflation ends by slow-rolling of the inflaton field ϕ which gets rapid at the end. Chaotic inflation or polynomial like fields ϕ^n are one of the type of such methods. Contrary to slow-roll approach, first-order phase transition works by using two fields such as ϕ and σ . The ϕ field slow rolls and becomes responsible for the extensive first-order phase transition of the σ field with bubble production mechanism. Similar to these models, hybrid models were given to incorporate problems introduced by the bubble formation mechanism. For instance, Linde [27] proposed two kinds of interactive fields responsible for enough inflation to happen. One of the scalar field χ does water-fall transition due to influence of slow-rollover of the other scalar field ϕ . The water-fall field χ is considered in a way that ϕ reaches some critical point and inflation ends at $\phi = \phi_c$. Hybrid Inflationary Model is also appeared to be important in resolving the fine tuning problems.

4.2 Hybrid Potential in Chaotic Inflation

In this section, we will consider chaotic polynomial like $\lambda_p \phi^p$ potential in hybrid model of inflation. We will analyze it for different values of p such $p = \frac{2}{3}, 1, 2, 4$ and calculate their relevant inflationary parameters. The tree-level predictions of these models will be considered under the light of the recent observations of the Planck's data. These models of inflation are well motivated to probe the predictions of inflation [31].

We will consider the Hybrid Inflation with Higgs potential $V(\chi)$ and Inflation potential $\delta V(\phi)$ and interaction term between the Higgs and Inflaton field, $g^2 \chi^2 \phi^2$. Such kind of hybrid potential can be expressed as

$$V(\chi, \phi) = \kappa^2 \left(M^2 - \frac{\chi^2}{4} \right)^2 + \frac{g^2 \chi^2 \phi^2}{4} + \delta V(\phi), \quad (4.1)$$

where $\delta V(\phi)$ is chaotic polynomial like potential of the form $\delta V(\phi) = \lambda_p \phi^p$ for $p > 0$. Whereas the interaction term $g^2 \chi^2 \phi^2$ utilized in generating the effective squared mass. The effective squared mass can be calculated by following this procedure which is taking the second derivative of potential with respect to χ .

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial V}{\partial \chi} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \chi} \left[\kappa^2 \left(M^2 - \frac{\chi^2}{4} \right)^2 + \frac{g^2 \chi^2 \phi^2}{4} + \delta V(\phi) \right], \\ \frac{\partial V}{\partial \chi} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \chi} \left[\left(\kappa^2 M^4 + \kappa^2 \frac{\chi^4}{16} - 2\kappa^2 \frac{M^2 \chi^2}{4} \right) + \frac{g^2 \chi^2 \phi^2}{4} + \delta V(\phi) \right], \\ \frac{\partial V}{\partial \chi} &= \left[\left(0 + 4\kappa^2 \frac{\chi^3}{16} - 4\kappa^2 \frac{M^2 \chi}{4} \right) + 2 \frac{g^2 \chi \phi^2}{4} + 0 \right], \\ \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial \chi^2} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial \chi} \left[\left(0 + 4\kappa^2 \frac{\chi^3}{16} - 4\kappa^2 \frac{M^2 \chi}{4} \right) + \frac{g^2 \chi \phi^2}{2} + 0 \right], \\ \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial \chi^2} &= \left[12\kappa^2 \frac{\chi^2}{16} - \kappa^2 M^2 + \frac{g^2 \phi^2}{2} \right], \\ \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial \chi^2} \Big|_{\chi=0} &= -\kappa^2 M^2 + \frac{g^2 \phi^2}{2}, \\ m_\chi^2 &= -\kappa^2 M^2 + \frac{g^2 \phi^2}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.2)$$

Factorizing eq. (4.2)

$$m_\chi^2 = \frac{g^2}{2} \left(\phi^2 - \frac{2\kappa^2 M^2}{g^2} \right), \quad \phi_c = \frac{\sqrt{2}\kappa M}{g}.$$

This is done for χ field in the $\chi = 0$ direction which is local minimum for the $\phi > \phi_c = \frac{\sqrt{2}\kappa M}{g}$. Therefore, in the $\chi = 0$ direction for equation (4.1), effective single field potential can be expressed uniquely in ϕ field.

$$V(\phi) = \kappa^2 M^4 + \delta V(\phi),$$

where $\delta V(\phi) = \lambda_p \phi^p$, and $V_0 = \kappa^2 M^4$

$$V(\phi) = \kappa^2 M^4 + \delta V(\phi) = V_0 + \lambda_p \phi^p. \quad (4.3)$$

It is evident from the above equation that fundamental constants such as κ , M , and g can be reduced to V_0 and ϕ^p alongwith independent parameter λ_p . The chaotic potential term provides the slope to make slow-roll inflation possible in the flat valley.

4.3 Slow-Roll Parameters

Slow-roll parameters are significant for analysis of predictions of inflationary regime. Therefore, we will focus on calculating the relevant slow-roll parameters and observables related to the Hybrid inflation paradigm. Rewriting the eq. (4.3) to develop convenient form for analytical and numerical calculations. Relevant numerical calculations and viability of the model according to the Planck's data will be discussed in the next chapter.

$$V(\phi) = V_0 + \lambda_p \phi^p,$$

Taking V_0 common out of the equation and replacing $\frac{\lambda_p}{V_0} = c$, for making it more simpler.

$$V = V_0(1 + c\phi^p). \quad (4.4)$$

Calculating first and second derivatives of the potentials for further use.

$$V' = \frac{d}{d\phi}(V_0 + V_0c\phi^p) = 0 + V_0cp\phi^{p-1} = V_0cp\phi^{p-1}. \quad (4.5)$$

Second derivative is given by,

$$V'' = \frac{d^2}{d\phi^2}(V_0cp\phi^{p-1}) = V_0cp(p-1)\phi^{p-2}. \quad (4.6)$$

After calculating the derivatives, we would consider the Slow-Roll Parameter ϵ . The expression of ϵ is given by

$$\epsilon = \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{V'(\phi)}{V(\phi)} \right)^2, \quad (4.7)$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{V_0cp\phi^{p-1}}{V_0(1 + c\phi^p)} \right)^2,$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi^{p-1}}{1 + c\phi^p} \right)^2. \quad (4.8)$$

Similarly, Slow-roll Parameter η is given as:

$$\eta = m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{V''(\phi)}{V(\phi)} \right). \quad (4.9)$$

V'' is calculated in eq. (4.6):

$$\eta = m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{V_0cp(p-1)\phi^{p-2}}{V_0(1 + c\phi^p)} \right),$$

$$\eta = m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp(p-1)\phi^{p-2}}{1 + c\phi^p} \right). \quad (4.10)$$

Number of e-folds, a measure of inflation, is given by following expression:

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{V(\phi)}{V'(\phi)} \right) d\phi, \quad (4.11)$$

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{V_0(1 + c\phi^p)}{V_0 c p \phi^{p-1}} \right) d\phi,$$

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{1 + c\phi^p}{c p \phi^{p-1}} \right) d\phi, \quad (4.12)$$

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{1}{c p \phi^{p-1}} \right) d\phi + \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{c\phi^p}{c p \phi^{p-1}} \right) d\phi,$$

For $p \neq 2$:

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \frac{1}{p} \left[\int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{1}{c \phi^{p-1}} \right) d\phi + \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{\phi^p}{\phi^{p-1}} \right) d\phi \right], \quad (4.13)$$

Taking p common out of the equation and dealing with the integrals.

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2 p} \left[\int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{1}{\phi^{p-1}} \right) + \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{\phi^p}{\phi^{p-1}} \right) \right],$$

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2 p} \left[\frac{1}{c} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \phi^{1-p} d\phi + \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \phi^{p-p+1} d\phi \right],$$

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2 p} \left[\frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{\phi_0^{2-p} + \phi_e^{2-p}}{2-p} \right) + \frac{\phi_0^2 + \phi_e^2}{2} \right].$$

As we observe that there will be singularity if we will take $p = 2$, this will enforce us to calculate Number of e-folds N for $p = 2$ separately.

$$N = \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2 p} \left[\frac{1}{2c} \left(\frac{\phi_0^{2-p} + \phi_e^{2-p}}{1 - \frac{p}{2}} \right) + \frac{\phi_0^2 + \phi_e^2}{2} \right],$$

$$N = \frac{1}{2m_{pl}^2 p} \left[\frac{1}{c} \left(\frac{\phi_0^{2-p} + \phi_e^{2-p}}{1 - \frac{p}{2}} \right) + \phi_0^2 + \phi_e^2 \right]. \quad (4.14)$$

For p=2:

Rewriting eq. (4.13) for $p = 2$,

$$\begin{aligned}
N &= \frac{1}{2m_{pl}^2} \left[\int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{1}{c\phi^{2-1}} \right) + \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{\phi^2}{\phi^{2-1}} \right) \right], \\
N &= \frac{1}{2m_{pl}^2} \left[\frac{1}{c} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{1}{\phi} \right) + \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \phi \right], \\
N &= \frac{1}{2m_{pl}^2} \left[\frac{1}{c} \ln(\phi_0 - \phi_e) + \frac{\phi_0^2 + \phi_e^2}{2} \right], \\
N &= \frac{1}{2m_{pl}^2} \left[\frac{1}{c} \ln \left(\frac{\phi_0}{\phi_e} \right) + \frac{\phi_0^2 + \phi_e^2}{2} \right]. \tag{4.15}
\end{aligned}$$

The curvature perturbation constraint which is physical observable and has fixed value. The expression of A_s can be calculated by following this procedure

$$A_s = \frac{1}{24\pi^2 m_{pl}^4} \frac{V}{\epsilon}, \tag{4.16}$$

From eq. (4.4) and eq. (4.8), substituting V and ϵ

$$\begin{aligned}
A_s &= \frac{1}{24\pi^2 m_{pl}^4} \frac{V_0(1 + c\phi^p)}{\frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi^{p-1}}{1 + c\phi^p} \right)^2}, \\
A_s &= \frac{1}{12\pi^2 m_{pl}^6} \frac{V_0(1 + c\phi^p)}{\left(\frac{cp\phi^{p-1}}{1 + c\phi^p} \right)^2}, \\
A_s &= \frac{1}{12\pi^2 m_{pl}^6} \frac{V_0(1 + c\phi^p)^3}{(cp\phi^{p-1})^2}. \tag{4.17}
\end{aligned}$$

The cosmological perturbations tensor-to-scalar ratio r and scalar spectral index n_s are given by following relations,

$$r \simeq 16\epsilon, \tag{4.18}$$

$$n_s \simeq 1 - 6\epsilon + 2\eta, \tag{4.19}$$

ϵ is given by the eq. (4.8), substituting it

$$r \simeq 16 \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1}}{1+c\phi_0^p} \right)^2,$$

$$r \simeq 8m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1}}{1+c\phi_0^p} \right)^2. \quad (4.20)$$

ϵ is given by the eq. (4.8) and η by eq. (4.10)

$$n_s \simeq 1 - 6 \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1}}{1+c\phi_0^p} \right)^2 + 2m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp(p-1)\phi_0^{p-2}}{1+c\phi_0^p} \right),$$

$$n_s \simeq 1 - 3m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1}}{1+c\phi_0^p} \right)^2 + 2m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp(p-1)\phi_0^{p-2}}{1+c\phi_0^p} \right). \quad (4.21)$$

4.4 Numerical Analysis

This section portrays different numerical solutions of Hybrid Potentials in Chaotic Inflation. Different exponents such as 1, 2/3, 2, 4 has been taken and studied under light of recent observations of Planck's data.

4.4.1 ϕ^1 plots

Figure 4.1: $\frac{\phi_0}{m_{pl}}$ vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$ and different values of c .

ϕ_0 is varying with $M^{-\frac{4}{3}}$ with other dominant term $-\frac{1}{c}$ depicted by figure (5.1). Different values of c are determining the variation in M . A_s is curvature perturbation constraint given as $A_s = 2.196 \times 10^{-9}$ and Planck's mass $m_{pl} = 2.435 \times 10^{18}$.

$$\phi_0 = -\frac{1}{c} + \frac{3^{\frac{1}{3}} A_s^{\frac{1}{3}} m_{pl}^2 (2\pi)^{\frac{2}{3}}}{c^{\frac{1}{3}} \kappa^{\frac{2}{3}} M^{\frac{4}{3}}}, \quad (4.22)$$

ϕ_0 can be determined by substituting different values of M , while all others are constants. ϕ_0 is characteristic for the field value at the beginning of inflation. Dividing it by m_{pl} gives the cut-off scale of the field. The field is found to lie in trans-planckian regime almost in all cases of ϕ , although M can be brought down to less than of Planck's mass m_{pl} .

Figure 4.2: n_s vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

Scalar spectral index n_s is significant predication parameter for inflationary cosmology which signifies the cosmological perturbations responsible for large-scale structure formation of the universe. The relationship between n_s , scalar spectral index, evaluated at $N_0 = 60$ with $M^{\frac{8}{3}}$ is given by eq. (4.23)

$$n_s \approx 1 - \frac{\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)^{\frac{1}{3}} c^{\frac{2}{3}} \kappa^{\frac{4}{3}} M^{\frac{8}{3}}}{2A_s^{\frac{2}{3}} m_{pl}^2 \pi^{\frac{4}{3}}}. \quad (4.23)$$

Figure 4.3: r vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

Tensor to scalar ratio, r , is also varying with $M^{\frac{8}{3}}$, whereas different c suggesting variation in M . Relation between r and M is depicted by the following approximate relation. The bound on r is $r < 0.056$.

$$r \approx \frac{2 \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\frac{2}{3}} c^{\frac{2}{3}} \kappa^{\frac{4}{3}} M^{\frac{8}{3}}}{A_s^{\frac{2}{3}} m_{pl}^2 \pi^{\frac{4}{3}}}. \quad (4.24)$$

Figure 4.4: n_s vs r for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

By using following expressions, one can calculate relevant n_s and r at ϕ . The

variation for both n_s and r is apparent by the change of ϕ . Although, r and n_s are calculated on ϕ_0 . It is visible that n_s does lie into the bounds of Planck's 2018 data [32]. The bound of n_s given by the recent data is $0.9607 \leq n_s \leq 0.9691$. The empirical bounds are important to distinguish different models of inflation on the basis of predictions. In all of the next plots, we will consider these bounds. The bound on r is $r < 0.056$.

$$n_s = 1 - \frac{3c^2 m_{pl}^2}{(1 + c\phi)^2} \quad ; \quad r = \frac{8c^2 m_{pl}^2}{(1 + c\phi)^2}. \quad (4.25)$$

4.4.2 $\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}$ plots

Figure 4.5: $\frac{\phi_0}{m_{pl}}$ vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

In the case of $\phi = \frac{2}{3}$, the relationship of ϕ_0 with respect to M is developed by the following approximate expression.

$$\phi_0 \approx \frac{2\sqrt{2} \left(\frac{A_s m_{pl}^6}{c\kappa^2 M^4} \right)^{\frac{3}{8}} \pi^{\frac{3}{4}}}{3^{\frac{3}{8}}}, \quad (4.26)$$

The role of c is found to be similar as the $\phi = 1$ which signifies difference in M values. The relationship between c and M is also inversely proportional. For larger values of c , M is shown to be decreasing in the fig. (4.5).

Figure 4.6: n_s vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different slices of c .

The approximate relation between n_s and M for the case of $\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}$ is deduced as the following expression.

$$n_s \approx 1 - \frac{3^{\frac{1}{4}} c m_{pl}^2 \left(3^{\frac{1}{4}} + 8c \left(\frac{A_s m_{pl}^6}{c \kappa^2 M^4} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{\pi} \right)}{\sqrt{\frac{A_s m_{pl}^6}{c \kappa^2 M^4}} \left(3 + 2 \times 3^{\frac{3}{4}} c \left(\frac{A_s m_{pl}^6}{c \kappa^2 M^4} \right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{\pi} \right)^2 \pi}. \quad (4.27)$$

Figure 4.7: r vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

Similarly, r can be approximately evaluated in context of M by using the eq.

(4.28). The expression for r vs M is satisfied by fig. (4.7).

$$r \approx \frac{16 \times 3^{\frac{1}{4}} c^2 m_{pl}^2}{\left(\frac{A_s m_{pl}^6}{c \kappa^2 M^4}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \left(3 + 2 \times 3^{\frac{3}{4}} c \left(\frac{A_s m_{pl}^6}{c \kappa^2 M^4}\right)^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{\pi}\right)^2 \cdot \sqrt{\pi}} \quad (4.28)$$

Figure 4.8: n_s vs r for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

The n_s and r can be evaluated in the following manner in order to make predictions. n_s is red tilted in the case of $\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}$ which is emphasized by $n_s < 1$ for all values of ϕ_0 . Also, n_s is in the bounds of Planck's data for $\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}$. But r is shown to be just inside the Planck's bounds. It can be reduced further which will see in the later chapters.

$$n_s = 1 - \frac{4cm_{pl}^2}{9 \left(1 + c\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}\right) \phi^{\frac{4}{3}}} - \frac{4c^2 m_{pl}^2}{3 \left(1 + c\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}\right)^2 \phi^{\frac{2}{3}}} \quad ; \quad r = \frac{32c^2 m_{pl}^2}{9 \left(1 + c\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}\right)^2 \phi^{\frac{2}{3}}}, \quad (4.29)$$

For instance, for a field ϕ_0 of value 2.179×10^{19} for $c = 4.051 \times 10^{-6}$ is yielded as 0.97 approximately. On the similar ground, r can be found. The variation of n_s and r is due to freedom of parameteric space.

4.4.3 ϕ^2 plots

Figure 4.9: $\frac{\phi_0}{m_{pl}}$ vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different slices of c .

ϕ_0 varies linearly with M^{-1} where as c has different slices as given in the fig. (4.9).

The behavior of ϕ_0 is exhibited by the eq. (4.30) with fixed value of κ .

$$\phi_0 \approx \frac{2 \times 3^{\frac{1}{3}} A_s^{\frac{1}{4}} m_{pl}^{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{\pi}}{c^{\frac{1}{4}} \sqrt{\kappa} M}. \quad (4.30)$$

Figure 4.10: n_s vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

The relationship between n_s and M for ϕ^2 is implied by th eq. (4.31).

$$n_s \approx 1 + \frac{4c\kappa M^2 m_{pl}^2 (\kappa M^2 - 8\sqrt{3}\sqrt{A_s}\sqrt{c}m_{pl}^3\pi)}{(\kappa M^2 + 4\sqrt{3}\sqrt{A_s}\sqrt{c}m_{pl}^3\pi)^2}. \quad (4.31)$$

Figure 4.11: r vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

Case of r is no different than the n_s , it has also gotten worse implied by the approximate relation (4.32).

$$r \approx \frac{128\sqrt{3}\sqrt{A_s}c^{\frac{3}{2}}\kappa M^2 m_{pl}^5 \pi}{(\kappa M^2 + 4\sqrt{3}\sqrt{A_s}\sqrt{c}m_{pl}^3\pi)^2}. \quad (4.32)$$

Figure 4.12: n_s vs r for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$ and values slices of c .

n_s and r , for ϕ^2 can be calculated by the eq. (4.33). The eq. (4.33) satisfies the fig. (4.12).

$$n_s = 1 - \frac{12c^2 m_{pl}^2 \phi^2}{(1 + c\phi^2)^2} + \frac{4cm_{pl}^2}{1 + c\phi^2} ; \quad r = \frac{32c^2 m_{pl}^2 \phi^2}{(1 + c\phi^2)^2}. \quad (4.33)$$

4.4.4 ϕ^4 plots

Figure 4.13: $\frac{\phi_0}{m_{pl}}$ vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-8}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

The variation of ϕ_0 with respect to M is of $M^{-\frac{2}{3}}$. Similar feature of c is visible by the fig. (4.13).

$$\phi_0 \approx \frac{2 \times 3^{\frac{1}{6}} A_s^{\frac{1}{6}} m_{pl} \pi^{\frac{1}{3}}}{c^{\frac{1}{6}} \kappa^{\frac{1}{3}} M^{\frac{2}{3}}}, \quad (4.34)$$

The field values for ϕ_0 in this case are super-planckian whereas M is less than m_{pl} . The evolution of the field is inversely related and it is clearly depicted that as the field ϕ value increases, M starts to decrease. All other quantities play role of constants. It is been studied that predictions of ϕ^4 is ruled out by the Planck's data.

Figure 4.14: n_s vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-8}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

The behavior of n_s in relation to M for ϕ^4 can be assessed by the expression (4.35) which agrees the fig. (4.14).

$$n_s \approx 1 + \frac{96 \left(3^{\frac{1}{3}} A_s^{\frac{1}{3}} c^{\frac{2}{3}} \kappa^2 M^4 m_{pl}^4 \pi^{\frac{2}{3}} - 48 A_s c \kappa^{\frac{2}{3}} M^{\frac{4}{3}} m_{pl}^8 \pi^2 \right)}{\left(\kappa^{\frac{4}{3}} M^{\frac{8}{3}} + 16 \times 3^{\frac{2}{3}} A_s^{\frac{2}{3}} c^{\frac{1}{3}} m_{pl}^4 \pi^{\frac{4}{3}} \right)^2}. \quad (4.35)$$

Figure 4.15: r vs $\log_{10} M$ for $\kappa = 10^{-8}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

r with respect to M in approximate relation can be found with eq. (4.36). For each

value of M , r can be estimated which agrees with the fig. (4.15).

$$r \approx \frac{24576 A_s c \kappa^{\frac{2}{3}} M^{\frac{4}{3}} m_{pl}^8 \pi^2}{\left(\kappa^{\frac{4}{3}} M^{\frac{8}{3}} + 16 \times 3^{\frac{2}{3}} A_s^{\frac{2}{3}} c^{\frac{1}{3}} m_{pl}^4 \pi^{\frac{4}{3}} \right)^2}. \quad (4.36)$$

Figure 4.16: n_s vs r for $\kappa = 10^{-8}$, $N_0 = 60$ and different values of c .

The estimates of n_s and r can be established by eq. (4.37). r is outside of the Planck's bounds in this case.

$$n_s = 1 - \frac{48c^2 m_{pl}^2 \phi^6}{(1 + c\phi^4)^2} + \frac{24cm_{pl}^2 \phi^2}{1 + c\phi^4} ; \quad r = \frac{128c^2 m_{pl}^2 \phi^6}{(1 + c\phi^4)^2}. \quad (4.37)$$

Chapter 5

Radiative Corrections in Hybrid Inflation

5.1 Radiative Corrections: Why Needed?

There are certain modifications and theoretical methodologies to make the model of Chaotic Inflation empirically adequate. One of the fundamental technique is inspired from the Quantum Field Theory (QFT) especially from the Quantum Electrodynamics (QED) calculations in the perturbation theory - known as radiative corrections. Radiative corrections. These corrections, although, increase the complexity of the model by introducing extra factors in the scalar fields and there is emphasis on simplicity in the history of science as the guiding principle but radiative corrections also provide the mechanism of the reheating after the inflation ends. Therefore, it also has physical significance attached. It is necessary for the adequate description of inflationary models is that it achieves enough e-folds for solving the cosmological problems of the Big Bang Model and also provides the necessary environment for the reheating of the universe in order to establish the environment for the theoretical and experimental considerations of the big bang cosmology such as reheating, evolution of the universe, and nucleosynthesis. And, for such complete explanatory model of inflation, it is considered that inflation couples with the

other fields because there is necessity of coupling between the inflaton and Standard Model of Particle Physics. The emergence of radiative corrections can be conceptualized through decay of inflaton field, ϕ , into fermions or bosons through different interactions (In case of fermions, Yukawa interaction). Hence, The radiative corrections are well-motivated modifications in the model for incorporating reheating of the universe. It will be shown later on that how coupling of the inflaton with the other fields makes the data viable with the experimental results such as lowering down the scalar spectral index, n_s , and amplitude of primordial gravitational waves r . However, overall mechanism of the inflationary model remain unchanged by introducing such radiative corrections. The couplings with inflaton field has shown significant results in models of inflation.

5.2 Radiatively Corrected Hybrid Inflation

As we discussed earlier, the inflaton field can be coupled with fermions and bosons. We will consider interaction with the fermionic radiative correction. These corrections can be provided from the Yukawa interaction of inflaton with right-handed neutrinos. The fermionic radiative correction of type $A\phi^4 \ln \phi$ is taken. For fermionic radiative correction $A < 0$ while for bosonic radiative correction $A > 0$. The fermionic radiative corrections have shown to be effective in the similar studies.

In order to analyze the impact of the radiative correction, we are considering 1-loop Coleman-Weinberg potential.

$$V_{1-loop} = A\phi^4 \ln \left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_e} \right), \quad (5.1)$$

Now, we will write down the Radiatively Corrected Hybrid Inflation Potential,

$$V = V_0 + \lambda_p \phi^p - A\phi^4 \ln \left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_e} \right), \quad (5.2)$$

Taking V_0 common out of the eq. (5.2),

$$V = V_0 \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_p \phi^p}{V_0} - \frac{A \phi^4 \ln\left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_e}\right)}{V_0} \right), \quad (5.3)$$

Rewriting the eq. (5.3) by doing simple substitution for the analytical and numerical convenience.

$$\tilde{A} = \frac{|A| \ln\left(\frac{\phi}{\phi_e}\right)}{V_0}, \quad c = \frac{\lambda_p}{V_0}.$$

Now, eq.(5.3) has taken the following form,

$$V = V_0 \left(1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4 \right). \quad (5.4)$$

We will use the eq. (5.4) and calculate the relevant Slow-Roll Parameters in the next subsection.

5.3 Slow-Roll Parameters with Radiatively Corrected Hybrid Inflation

To consider the predictions of Radiatively Correction Hybrid Inflation, Slow-Roll Parameters will be calculated.

Rewriting the eq. (5.4) and calculating first two derivatives for further use.

$$V = V_0 \left(1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4 \right), ,$$

$$V' = V_0 c p \phi^{p-1} - 4V_0 \tilde{A} \phi^3. \quad (5.5)$$

Similarly, second derivative is given by,

$$V'' = V_0 c p (p-1) \phi^{p-2} - 12V_0 \tilde{A} \phi^2. \quad (5.6)$$

Restating expression for the Slow-Roll Parameter ϵ from eq. (4.7)

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon &= \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{V'(\phi)}{V(\phi)} \right)^2, \\ \epsilon &= \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{V_0(cp\phi^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi^3)}{V_0(1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4)} \right)^2, \\ \epsilon &= \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi^3}{1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4} \right)^2.\end{aligned}\tag{5.7}$$

Doing similar calculation for the Slow-Roll Parameter η by using eq. (4.9) and using first derivative of the potential from eq. (5.5).

$$\begin{aligned}\eta &= m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{V''(\phi)}{V(\phi)} \right), \\ \eta &= m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{V_0(cp(p-1)\phi^{p-2} - 12\tilde{A}\phi^2)}{V_0(1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4)} \right), \\ \eta &= m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp(p-1)\phi^{p-2} - 12\tilde{A}\phi^2}{1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4} \right).\end{aligned}\tag{5.8}$$

Number of e-folds are given by eq. (4.11):

$$\begin{aligned}N &= \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{V(\phi)}{V'(\phi)} \right) d\phi, \\ N &= \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{V_0(1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4)}{V_0(cp\phi^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi^3)} \right), \\ N &= \frac{1}{m_{pl}^2} \int_{\phi_e}^{\phi_0} \left(\frac{1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4}{cp\phi^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi^3} \right).\end{aligned}\tag{5.9}$$

As done in the previous chapter, physical observable curvature perturbation constraint can be calculated by using following formula given in eq. (4.16)

$$A_s = \frac{1}{24\pi^2 m_{pl}^4} \frac{V}{\epsilon},$$

$$\begin{aligned}
A_s &= \frac{1}{24\pi^2 m_{pl}^4} \frac{V_0 (1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4)}{\frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi^3}{1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4} \right)^2}, \\
A_s &= \frac{1}{12\pi^2 m_{pl}^6} \frac{V_0 (1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4)}{\left(\frac{cp\phi^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi^3}{1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4} \right)^2}, \\
A_s &= \frac{1}{12\pi^2 m_{pl}^6} \frac{V_0 (1 + c\phi^p - \tilde{A}\phi^4)^3}{\left(cp\phi^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi^3 \right)^2}. \tag{5.10}
\end{aligned}$$

The relation for tensor to scalar ratio r and scalar spectral index n_s is given by eqs. (4.18) and (4.19) respectively.

$$r \simeq 16\epsilon.$$

$$n_s \simeq 1 - 6\epsilon + 2\eta.$$

The expression for r is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
r &\simeq 16 \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi_0^3}{1 + c\phi_0^p - \tilde{A}\phi_0^4} \right)^2, \\
r &\simeq 8m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi_0^3}{1 + c\phi_0^p - \tilde{A}\phi_0^4} \right)^2. \tag{5.11}
\end{aligned}$$

On similar note, the expression for n_s is following:

$$\begin{aligned}
n_s &\simeq 1 - 6 \frac{m_{pl}^2}{2} \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi_0^3}{1 + c\phi_0^p - \tilde{A}\phi_0^4} \right)^2 + 2m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp(p-1)\phi_0^{p-2} - 12\tilde{A}\phi_0^2}{1 + c\phi_0^p - \tilde{A}\phi_0^4} \right), \\
n_s &\simeq 1 - 3m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp\phi_0^{p-1} - 4\tilde{A}\phi_0^3}{1 + c\phi_0^p - \tilde{A}\phi_0^4} \right)^2 + 2m_{pl}^2 \left(\frac{cp(p-1)\phi_0^{p-2} - 12\tilde{A}\phi_0^2}{1 + c\phi_0^p - \tilde{A}\phi_0^4} \right). \tag{5.12}
\end{aligned}$$

5.4 Numerical Results

5.4.1 ϕ^1 Radiatively Corrected Plots

Figure 5.1: $\frac{\phi_0}{m_{pl}}$ vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

The relationship of ϕ_0 with coupling A is considered by fig. 5.1 for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$ at Number of e-folds $N_0 = 60$. The different values of c lowering down A while increasing the field ϕ_0 value.

Figure 5.2: n_s vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

n_s is consistent with the bounds of Planck's data while for $c = 3.9 \times 10^{-15}$, lowest

value of A is achieved for n_s . The upper bound on A for the ϕ^1 is $A6 \times \leq 10^{-15}$ which are shown to be achieved.

Figure 5.3: r vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

r vs A is elaborated by the fig. 5.3, where lowest value of r is achieved by utilizing for $c = 3.9 \times 10^{-15}$ which is lowered down and inside the bounds of r .

Figure 5.4: r vs n_s for $\kappa = 10^{-1}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

The mutual relationship between n_s and r is evident by their behavior as shown in the fig. 5.4. Both n_s and r are consistent with the data.

5.4.2 $\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}$ Radiatively Corrected Plots

Figure 5.5: $\frac{\phi_0}{m_{Pl}}$ vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

Similar to ϕ^1 , the bound on A is $A \leq 6 \times 10^{-15}$ which is also attained for $\phi^{\frac{2}{3}}$. c is also appearing to be reason of lower values of A .

Figure 5.6: n_s vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

n_s is pretty much inside the bounds of data with lower and consistent values of A . This shows the influence of utilizing radiative corrections in the hybrid inflationary paradigm.

Figure 5.7: r vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

r is less than 0.056 which depicts that r value can be lowered down by introducing radiative corrections. Lowering of both n_s and r makes the chaotic polynomial like potentials viable.

Figure 5.8: r vs n_s for $\kappa = 10^{-5}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

r vs n_s shown together with their c values in fig. 5.8. n_s and r are the most important parameters for considering the predictions of any inflationary model. Therefore, consistency of these parameters with model is significant.

5.4.3 ϕ^2 Radiatively Corrected Plots

Figure 5.9: $\frac{\phi_0}{m_{pl}}$ vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

The relation of ϕ_0 with A is shown in the fig. 5.9. The upper bound on A for ϕ^2 is $A \leq 10^{-13}$ which could not be attained. Also, different values of c does not have greater influence on the behavior of A .

Figure 5.10: n_s vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

n_s is red-tilted in this case and is under the bounds of Planck's observations. It is evident now that for both without radiative corrections and with radiative corrections, observables get worse for increasing p value.

Figure 5.11: r vs $\frac{A}{10^{-15}}$ for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

The prediction of r is also not improved that much for ϕ^2 but gets inside the bounds of r as shown by the fig. 5.11.

Figure 5.12: r vs n_s for $\kappa = 10^{-2}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

n_s and r are shown in the fig. 5.12. For the values for which n_s is inside the data, r is outside the bounds. Therefore, the models of ϕ^2 and greater powers are not quite good for predictions of phenomenological inflation.

5.4.4 ϕ^4 Radiatively Corrected Plots

Figure 5.13: r vs n_s for $\kappa = 10^{-8}$, $N_0 = 60$, fixed M and different values of c .

For ϕ^4 , r is not consistent with the data. Whereas n_s is shown to be getting more blue-tilted as approaching the value of 0.99. The influence of different c is not that extraordinary and all of plots overlap on each other.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

The success of Big Bang Model has made remarkable changes in the chronological understanding of our universe. Though consisting of explanatory simplicity, Big Bang Model contain certain errors for which different remedies have been produced over the years. In this thesis, one of the phenomenological approach, inspired by particle physics, Inflation has been elucidated. Inflation solves the cosmological puzzles; horizon problem, flatness problem, and magnetic monopoles problem through proposal of accelerated expansion of the universe at early stages. The proposition of accelerated expansion has far reaching consequences. For instance, it solves the Big Bang Model puzzles by reduction in comoving Hubble radius and negative pressures. The mimicry of behavior which allows dynamics of the universe evolve under the condition of negative pressure was core motivation behind inflationary solutions. Due to influence of particle physics, scalar field was hypothesized for setting the initial conditions for inflationary epoch to occur. Plethora of models and mechanisms have been developed since the emergence of inflation as paradigm. Fortunately, astrophysical observations have played a role to acquire more accurate and precise data for discriminating the utility of different models. We have studied Hybrid Inflation in chaotic polynomial like potentials $V(\phi) = V_0 + \lambda_p \phi^p$ to understand the extent of viability of these models. Certain powers of ϕ are considered such as 1, 2/3, 2 and 4. Slow-roll approximation is utilized for analysis of predictions of physical observables. The empirical adequacy of the predictions is studied through the window of Planck's

observational bounds. We found that for different powers of ϕ like 1, 2, 2/3, 4, the predictions single-field effective potential lies outside the bounds of Planck's data. But certain modifications can be applied to the potentials for studying their effects. In this case, specifically, radiative corrections are added to the single field effective potential. The type of radiative correction used for this purpose is fermionic radiative correction. Coupling of radiative corrections with inflaton field is also motivated scheme for producing the conditions for reheating process after the inflation. Radiatively Corrected Hybrid Inflation has appeared to make the models consistent for ϕ^1 and ϕ^2 by lowering down r and specifying red-tilted n_s . In case of ϕ^2 and ϕ^4 , the predictive parameters have gotten better but still does not lie inside the bounds of empirical data.

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